

SINGAPORE'S ANTI-CORRUPTION POLICY TO STRENGTHEN THE ECONOMIC SECURITY OF THE STATE

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Annotation. The article discusses the experience, features and characteristics of Singapore's modern anti-corruption policy, which served to strengthen the economic security of the state. The priority areas of Singapore's economic policy, which ensured the achievement of high results in the international arena, are also studied.

Key words: corruption, anti-corruption policy, export, investment, education, economic security.

Аннотация. Мақолада Сингапурнинг давлатнинг иқтисодий хавфсизлигини мустақамлашга хизмат қилган замонавий коррупцияга қарши сиёсатининг тажрибаси, хусусиятлари муҳокама қилинади. Сингапур иқтисодий сиёсатининг халқаро майдонда юксак натижаларга эришишни таъминлаган устувор йўналишлари ҳам қайд этилган.

Калит сўзлар: коррупция, коррупцияга қарши сиёсат, экспорт, сармоя, таълим, иқтисодий хавфсизлик.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается опыт, особенности и характерные черты современной антикоррупционной политики Сингапура, что послужило укреплению экономической безопасности государства. Также исследованы приоритетные направления экономической политики Сингапура, которые обеспечили достижение высоких результатов на международной арене.

Ключевые слова: коррупция, антикоррупционная политика, экспорт, инвестиции, образования, экономическая безопасность.

At the present stage of improving public administration, the governments of many countries are paying more and more attention to the introduction of practical measures of anti-corruption policy in order to fully increase the economic potential of the state. It is well known that the harmful consequences of corruption completely impede the development of the state and society. Since corruption "is an extremely negative phenomenon that distorts the development of business, reduces the effectiveness of public administration, incentives for investment, hinders the economic and political development of the country, and creates social inequality" [1].

This, as a systemic phenomenon, is the source of the main dangers and threats to the economic security of the state. It is worth noting the desire of many states to form an effective legislative anti-corruption framework, which really constructively contributed to ensuring the economic security of the state. One of these states is Singapore, as an industrial country began a comprehensive fight against corruption by raising the level of moral values of the population and improving the professionalism of civil servants.

In order to strengthen the economic security of the state, Singapore's anti-corruption policy provides for the implementation of three priority tasks: the elimination of bribe takers and various elements of bribery at all levels of government; elimination of bureaucratic procedures and the introduction of strict legal regulation of the rights and obligations of state officials, monitoring the observance of ethical norms of official behavior by civil servants.

In this context, it should be emphasized that the determining factor in the country's anti-corruption policy is the salary of an official. After all, a decent salary for an official instills decency and conscientiousness in interpersonal relationships.

According to Lee Kuan Yew, political leaders should be paid the highest salaries because they deserve it by being a decent and honest government. If they are underpaid, they may be tempted to engage in corrupt activities [2]. This, in turn, served as the basis for the development and practical implementation of a comprehensive system of anti-corruption measures.

In addition, Singapore has a socially oriented anti-corruption law (1937) "On Combating Corruption". And in 1960, the "Corruption Prevention Act" was adopted, pursuing two goals: to neutralize the corruption articles of national legislation and to toughen the punishment for bribery. Also, this Act provides for the indexation and constant increase in the wages of civil servants; improvement of procedures for interaction with citizens, enterprises and organizations in order to eliminate bureaucratic delays; ensuring proper transparency of control and supervision; rotation of personnel to avoid the formation of stable corruption ties; ensuring a confidentiality regime to prevent leakage of insider information.

According to scientific sources, as a priority measure in the fight against corruption, the leadership of Singapore has identified the following:

- Creation of more modern anti-corruption legislation;
- Establishment of a special maximum independent state body to combat corruption;

- tougher criminal liability for corruption;
- establishment of high social guarantees for state and municipal employees;
- the practice of constant and systematic rotation of managerial personnel;
- legislative guarantees for the safety of a person and his family members who testified on the fact of corruption;
- wide coverage of anti-corruption activities in the media;
- conducting an independent examination of laws and regulations for corruption consequences [3].

The foundation for the above measures was the established principles of anti-corruption policy: the responsibility of both parties to corruption relations; delimitation of public and private interests; equality of all before the law and court; de-bureaucratization of the apparatus - minimization of documentary circulation, personal example of the leader; career growth based on personal merits and achievements, rather than family or friendly ties; decent salary; controllability - unforeseen business checks, declaration of income, property and debts, prosecutorial checks of bank, stock and settlement accounts suspected of being involved in corrupt transactions.

Consequently, the positive tone of Singapore's anti-corruption policy is reflected in the positions of international ratings. As a result of ongoing pragmatic reforms, according to the Corruption Perceptions Index for 2022, published by the international non-governmental organization Transparency International, Singapore ranks 5th in the ranking and is among the states least affected by corruption. According to the Global Data Country Risk Index, in 2020 Singapore was ranked 2nd in the world among the least risky countries for investment, due to political stability, low levels of corruption and transparency of government institutions. The guarantee of the country as a reliable business partner is an independent judiciary, pragmatic monetary and fiscal policy [4].

Undoubtedly, the purposeful implementation of a continuous anti-corruption policy by the leadership of Singapore has transformed the economic model with a developed infrastructure system and a high share of exports of products such as information technology, consumer electronics, pharmaceuticals and financial services. It follows that an important role in the economic development of Singapore is played by foreign trade, which serves as the main source of income for the country. Export helps the country to export more than half of domestic products on the world market, to provide foreign exchange earnings as a guarantor of socio-economic development.

Undoubtedly, Singapore is a major player in international trade. According to the World Trade Organization for 2021, the country ranked 14th in the world in terms of exports and 15th in terms of imports. Singapore's exports in 2021 amounted to \$363 billion, while imports amounted to \$330 billion. Moreover, it is important to highlight that Singapore's economy is one of the most open and free from corruption; in 2021, the country ranks 37th among the largest economies in the world, with a GDP of \$397 billion. The country maintains stable prices, and GDP per capita is one of the highest in the world - about 73 thousand dollars [6,7].

We would like to highlight that the following features contributed to the achievement of the above results and the strengthening of Singapore's economic security:

- rational tax policy, attracting foreign entrepreneurs. Thus, the company's income is taxed at a flat rate of 18%. There is a single-level system of taxation of companies, which is a powerful tool for managing the economy in market conditions;

- Singapore ranks 2nd in the world for ease of doing business. To register a company, you need to go through 3 procedures, which will take no more than 2.5 days. The cost of registering a business is 0.6% of income per capita, and the minimum authorized capital is 0;

- State support and a huge number of preferences for enterprises. Singapore has concessional lending programs for small businesses, which provide for the issuance of special loans and the provision of subsidies. Within the framework of the iSPRINT program (a state project of financial support in the amount of 20 thousand dollars to cover the costs of acquiring advanced IT programs for managing sales and finance, as well as hardware and software, etc.) in more than 5 thousand small and medium-sized companies' business implemented information and communication solutions;

- program of training and retraining of specialists. The state pays up to 90% for training and retraining of personnel. The share of people with higher education is more than 50%. Approximately 39% of the state budget is allocated to finance the education system. At the same time, large national companies widely use the experience of financing training and advanced training of their personnel. Universities have good material and technical support and high employment opportunities for graduates. The system of vocational education includes vocational schools with a period of study from several months to 1-2 years, 5-year technical colleges for training personnel in 20 engineering

specialties based on a 9-year school, as well as special training schools (1- and 4-year);

- lack of a centralized public procurement system. Procurement is carried out by individual ministries, departments and bodies provided for by law. This policy is formulated by the Ministry of Finance, which seeks to ensure the transparency and fairness of public procurement.

Having created favorable conditions for investment attractiveness, the government of Singapore began to pay great attention to the technical development of the country. Top research priorities as defined by the National Research Foundation: biomedical sciences; environmental protection and water treatment technologies: clean water and green energy; interactive and digital media.

This, in turn, has made Singapore a world leader in innovation. So, the state spent about 2% of GDP on research and development in 2020 [8].

Thus, Singapore was able to achieve a fruitful strengthening of the economic security of the state through the political will of the leaders and competent anti-corruption legislation, which ensured high people's trust in the government. Trust is not only a barometer of the active participation of the population in public administration, but also the most valuable asset of the Singapore government, which has formed a high moral climate in the country's society. Also, the systemic fight against corruption has become a catalyst in increasing the economic potential, improving the image and authority of the country in the international arena, which ensured the minimization or exclusion of conditions that create both an incentive and the possibility of inducing a person to commit corrupt acts.

References:

1. Shurygin, F. F. Anti-corruption policy of the Republic of Singapore / F. F. Shurygin. — Text: direct // Young scientist. - 2015. - No. 22 (102). - S. 681-691. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/102/23444/>
2. Shurygin, F. F. Anti-corruption policy of the Republic of Singapore / F. F. Shurygin. — Text: direct // Young scientist. - 2015. - No. 22 (102). - S. 681-691. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/102/23444/>
3. Fundamentals of anti-corruption culture. Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Astana 2016. pp. 24-25. <https://ksph.edu.kz/files>
4. <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2022>
5. World Trade Statistical Review 2021. https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/statis_e/wts2021_e/wts2021_e.pdf

6. World Data. info. <https://www.worlddata.info/largest-economies.php>
7. World Data. info. <https://www.worlddata.info/largest-economies.php>
8. Analysis of the features of the economic development of the countries of Southeast Asia (Singapore, Malaysia). <http://isrs.uz/ru/tahliliy-sharhlar/analiz-osobennostej-ekonomiceskogo-razvitia-stran-uva-singapura-malajzii>

